

Pre-Fixation Compression Screw Technique for Varus Correction in Proximal Femoral Nailing of Intertrochanteric Fractures**Vishal Kumar Sharma¹, Abu Ghufuran², Narendra Kumar Sinha³, Jitendra Kumar⁴, Rupesh Kumar Mahato⁵, Om Prakash⁶**¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India³Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India⁴JR (Academic-2), Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India⁵PG-JR-1, Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India⁶Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This study evaluated the efficacy of the pre-fixation compression screw technique for varus correction in proximal femoral nailing of intertrochanteric fractures. A cohort of 20 patients underwent surgical intervention using this technique, with outcomes measured through varus angle correction, Harris Hip Score improvements, time to fracture healing, and complication rates. Results demonstrated significant varus correction and improved functional outcomes with minimal complications. The technique facilitated early mobilization and a high rate of fracture healing within six months, suggesting it is a viable option for enhancing clinical outcomes in intertrochanteric fracture surgeries.

Keywords: Intertrochanteric Fractures, Varus Correction, Proximal Femoral Nailing, Pre-Fixation Compression Screw.

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Introduction

Intertrochanteric fractures represent a significant challenge in orthopedic practice, particularly due to their frequency in the elderly population and their association with osteoporosis [1]. The management of these fractures aims to achieve stable fixation, allowing for early mobilization and weight-bearing to minimize complications associated with patient immobility [2]. Proximal femoral nailing has become a standard treatment modality for these fractures due to its biomechanical advantages and minimally invasive approach, providing better stabilization and reduced healing times [3].

However, achieving optimal alignment, particularly varus correction, remains a critical factor in the success of the surgical outcome [4]. Varus malalignment is a common complication that can lead to increased mechanical stress on the implant and the bone, potentially resulting in fixation failure or delayed union [5]. Traditional techniques of proximal femoral nailing, while effective, often do

not adequately address the challenge of correcting varus deformity during the procedure. The technique of pre-fixation involves a few critical steps to achieve varus correction during proximal femoral nailing. Initially, a guide wire is accurately placed to define the path for the compression screw. Following this, a pre-fixation compression screw is inserted along the guide wire to adjust and correct any varus deformity, setting the stage for the proximal femoral nail. This pre-fixation adjustment is key as it provides initial stabilization and correct alignment of the bone segments before the definitive nailing is performed. By doing so, it helps ensure that the nail can be inserted in the most biomechanically advantageous position, which is crucial for optimal post-operative outcomes and stability [6-8]. This study aims to assess the effectiveness of the pre-fixation compression screw technique for achieving varus correction during proximal femoral nailing in patients with intertrochanteric fractures.

Specifically, the study seeks to evaluate the impact of this technique on achieving optimal post-operative alignment, enhancing functional recovery, reducing the time to fracture healing, and minimizing complications associated with traditional nailing methods.

This research aims to provide empirical evidence to support the adoption of the pre-fixation compression screw technique in clinical practice, potentially setting a new standard for the surgical treatment of intertrochanteric fractures.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employs a prospective cohort design to evaluate the effectiveness of the pre-fixation compression screw technique for varus correction during proximal femoral nailing in patients with intertrochanteric fractures.

Study Population: The study will include 20 patients diagnosed with intertrochanteric fractures, recruited from a single tertiary care center. Inclusion criteria are adults aged 50 years and older with closed intertrochanteric fractures suitable for nailing. Exclusion criteria include patients with pathological fractures, previous hip surgeries, or those unable to undergo surgery due to medical comorbidities.

Intervention: Patients will undergo proximal femoral nailing with the application of a pre-fixation compression screw for varus correction. The procedure will be performed under general or spinal anesthesia based on the patient's health status and preference. Standard antiseptic techniques will be used, and the same surgical team will perform all procedures to ensure consistency.

Data Collection: Data will be collected at baseline (pre-operatively), immediately post-operatively, and at follow-up intervals of 1, 3, 6, and 12 months. The primary outcomes measured will include the degree of varus correction achieved, as assessed by post-operative radiographs. Secondary outcomes will focus on functional recovery using the Harris Hip Score, time to fracture healing on radiographs, and any surgical complications.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics will summarize the demographic and clinical

characteristics of the participants. The effectiveness of the varus correction will be assessed using paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, comparing pre- and post-operative angles. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis will be used to estimate the time to fracture healing, and logistic regression will analyze the predictors of complications.

Results

The study included 20 patients with a mean age of 72 years (range: 50-89 years). The sample consisted of 12 females and 8 males. All participants had sustained a closed intertrochanteric fracture from low-energy falls.

Surgical Outcomes: The application of the pre-fixation compression screw was successful in all 20 patients. The mean pre-operative varus angle was 15 degrees (SD = 3.2), which was significantly corrected post-operatively to a mean angle of 5 degrees (SD = 1.8), demonstrating a significant improvement ($p < 0.001$).

Functional Outcomes: Functional recovery assessed by the Harris Hip Score showed significant improvement. The mean score improved from 30 (indicating severe hip dysfunction) pre-operatively to 80 (good hip function) at the 12-month follow-up ($p < 0.001$).

Fracture Healing: Radiographic evidence indicated that 18 out of 20 patients (90%) achieved complete fracture healing by the 6-month follow-up. The remaining two patients showed delayed healing at the 12-month follow-up.

Complications: There were minimal complications reported. Two patients developed superficial surgical site infections, which were successfully treated with antibiotics. No major complications such as deep infection, non-union, or implant failure were observed.

Statistical Analysis: The results of paired t-tests confirmed the significant reduction in varus deformity ($p < 0.001$) and significant improvement in Harris Hip Scores ($p < 0.001$). Kaplan-Meier analysis showed a median time to fracture healing of 140 days, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 130 to 150 days.

Table 1: This table encapsulates the key data points and outcomes from the study, providing a clear overview of the effectiveness of the pre-fixation compression screw technique.

Measure	Value
Mean Age (years)	72 (Range: 50-89)
Gender Distribution (F)	12:8
Mean Pre-operative Varus Angle (degrees)	15 (SD = 3.2)
Mean Post-operative Varus Angle (degrees)	5 (SD = 1.8)
Mean Pre-operative Harris Hip Score	30
Mean 12-month Post-operative Harris Hip Score	80
Patients Achieving Fracture Healing by 6 Months	18/20 (90%)
Complications (Surgical Site Infections)	2/20 (10%)
Time to Fracture Healing (Median days)	140 (95% CI: 130-150)

Radiographs of a 56-year-old male with right sided type-II intertrochanteric fracture operated with PFN. (a and b) Pre-operative antero-posterior and lateral view radiographs showing type II intertrochanteric fracture. (c and d) Immediate post operative radiographs showing good reduction of fracture with PFN in-situ. (e and f) Antero-posterior and lateral radiographs showing union at 12 weeks of follow up [21].

Radiographs showing backing out of proximal cephalic screw with exuberant callus at the fracture site in a 60 year old patient treated with PFN [21].

Radiographs of a 71-year-old male patient with left sided type-II intertrochanteric fracture fixed with DHS. (a) Pre-operative antero-posterior view of left sided type II intertrochanteric fracture. (b and c) Immediate radiographs showing good reduction of fracture fragments with DHS in-situ. (d and e) Antero-posterior and lateral view radiographs showing good union at 12 weeks follow up [21].

Discussion

The introduction of the pre-fixation compression screw in proximal femoral nailing for intertrochanteric fractures has shown promising results, as evidenced by the significant improvement in post-operative varus correction angles in this study [9]. The reduction from a mean pre-operative varus angle of 15 degrees to 5 degrees post-operation not only supports the efficacy of this technique in achieving optimal alignment but also suggests a potential to reduce biomechanical stresses on the implant and surrounding bone structure, thereby possibly extending the longevity of the surgical repair [10,11].

Moreover, the functional outcomes, as indicated by the substantial improvement in the Harris Hip Scores from 30 pre-operatively to 80 at the 12-month follow-up, underline the clinical relevance of achieving proper alignment [12]. Better alignment correlates with improved load distribution during ambulation, which can enhance patient mobility and quality of life post-surgery. The high rate of fracture healing (90% by six months) further validates the technique's effectiveness in fostering an environment conducive to bone regeneration and healing [13,14,15].

The complication rate observed in this study was minimal, with only 10% of patients experiencing superficial surgical site infections, all of which were successfully managed with antibiotics [16]. This low complication rate is noteworthy, considering the potential complexities associated with surgical interventions in the elderly, who often present with comorbidities that could complicate both the surgery and the post-operative recovery phase [17,18].

This study's findings support the integration of the pre-fixation compression screw technique into standard practice for treating intertrochanteric fractures. Future studies might focus on comparing this technique directly with traditional methods to further elucidate its benefits, particularly concerning long-term outcomes like implant longevity and rates of revision surgery. Furthermore, expanding the sample size and including multiple centers could enhance the generalizability of these results and provide a more robust statistical analysis to validate these preliminary findings [19,20].

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that the use of a pre-fixation compression screw for varus correction in proximal femoral nailing significantly enhances post-operative alignment and functional outcomes in patients with intertrochanteric fractures. The technique not only achieved a substantial correction of varus deformity but also facilitated high rates of fracture healing and improved mobility, as reflected in the Harris Hip Scores. With minimal

complications reported, this approach shows considerable promise for standardizing treatment protocols in orthopedic surgery, potentially reducing the risk of long-term complications and improving the quality of life for patients. Further research with larger sample sizes and multi-center trials will be crucial to confirm these findings and potentially recommend widespread adoption of this technique in clinical practice.

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